

A statistical method for rapid determination of endurance limit based on a thermographic method

Ali Shahmirzaloo, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands, a.shahmirzaloo@tue.nl
Davide Leonetti, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands, d.leonetti@tue.nl
Faas Moonen, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands, s.p.g.moonen@tue.nl
Rijk Blok, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands, r.blok@tue.nl

ABSTRACT

The staircase method is traditionally employed to estimate the endurance limit, requiring to test of a relatively large number of specimens at several load levels to obtain a reliable dataset, making this procedure time-consuming and expensive. A rapid method, based on thermography is alternatively employed to estimate the endurance limit, intended as the fatigue strength at 1 or 2 million cycles. The procedure results in a relation between the stabilized temperature as a function of the maximum applied stress or amplitude and involves manual processing of the data to determine the endurance limit. The present paper presents a statistical model based on the Maximum Likelihood Method to estimate the endurance limit by the aforementioned thermographic method, which is automatic, and does not involve manual manipulation of the dataset.

KEYWORDS

Rapid method, stabilized temperature, endurance limit, thermographic method

INTRODUCTION

Aerospace, automotive, construction, and marine industries are increasingly using Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) composites [1]–[3] due to their high strength-to-weight ratio and stiffness-to-weight ratio. In recent years, the fatigue properties of FRP received increasing attention, because when subjected to cyclic loading during in-service life, the strength and stiffness of FRP structural components are severely degraded, affecting their safety. A key property of cyclic strength of material is the endurance limit, which is usually determined using advanced statistical models such as the random fatigue-limit model [4] and the generalized random fatigue limit model [5], [6] or the standard staircase method [7]. It is, however, required to test a relatively large number of specimens at different load levels using these methods [8]. According to BS 12107 standard [7] a preliminary estimate of the endurance limit by the staircase method requires a minimum of 15 specimens to determine the mean and standard deviation. Instead, a minimum of 30 specimens is required for reliable results. Therefore, determining the endurance limit is usually time consuming. Composite materials have a great diversity due to the fact that laminate stacking sequences and their orders affect material properties. As a result, several methods have been developed, to estimate endurance limit rapidly based on the X-ray [9]–[12], acoustic emission [13]–[16], mechanical analysis [17]–[20], simulation [21]–[24], and thermography.

The thermography method is based on self-heating phenomena and it has been used widely in engineering applications. It involves measuring the stabilized temperature of a specimen as a function of maximum applied stress, for a given stress ratio, R . Based on Fig. 1(a), it is observed that during a fatigue test, the temperature of a specimen exhibits an initial rapid increase followed by a tendency to reach a stable value. Furthermore, it is evident that as the maximum stress increases, with R constant, there is a corresponding increase in the value of the stabilized temperature. In order to determine the stabilized temperature value, it is not necessary to execute the fatigue test until specimen failures occur. Instead, a stepped loading is employed in this methodology. After a predetermined number of load cycles, the resultant stabilized temperature rise is recorded and maximum stress is increased.

A specimen loaded at a stress level below the endurance limit exhibits a different heat release, resulting in temperature increase, as compared to when it is loaded at a stress level larger than the endurance limit. Consequently, the endurance limit can be determined by measuring temperature at different stress levels, e.g. by using an infrared thermographic camera. For metallic materials, the stabilized

temperature at stress levels below the endurance limit shows a nearly horizontal trend. For this reason, Risitano [25] proposed a method involving one line to characterize the data that do not show a horizontal trend when plotted as stabilized temperature vs maximum applied stress. Therefore, in this method, the intersection of the line and horizontal axis is thought to be the endurance limit [24–28]. This method is also called the one-curve method (OCM). Luong [26] proposed to interpolate the experimental data by two lines, one for stresses below and the other for stresses above the endurance limit. In this method, also known as the two-curve method (TCM), the intersection of these two lines is indicated as an estimate of the endurance limit. Many researchers [27]–[32] applied both these methods indicating that they make it possible to estimate the endurance limit in a short time as compared to the staircase method for a variety of materials, such as steels, magnesium alloy, composite materials, and specimen shapes. The determination process of the OCM and the TCM is shown in Fig. 1(b) showing that the OCM produces more conservative results than the TCM.

Fig. 1 Calculation of the endurance limit using thermographic data. a) Temperature evolution during fatigue testing ΔT_{stab} : stabilized temperature; σ_{max} : maximum applied stress, $\sigma_{max,1} < \sigma_{max,2} < \sigma_{max,3}$. b) TCM and OCM methods for determining endurance limit

However, both methods involve user-dependent procedures, e.g. the division of the dataset prior to estimating the endurance limit, of which the outcome would influence the estimation. In practice, both methods require identifying a dramatic change in the trend of the stabilized temperature, ΔT_{stab} , versus maximum applied stress, σ_{max} . Based on this, the user is required to split the dataset into two subsets. Although for relatively scarce data the procedure is deemed to be straightforward and user-independent, this is not guaranteed for larger datasets. In [33] three methods have been proposed to overcome the aforementioned user-dependency. The second method proposed in [33], namely Method Two (M2), a continuous curve with three adjustable parameters is employed to fit the stabilized temperature, ΔT_{stab} , as a function of the maximum applied stress, σ_{max} . The minimum curvature radius derived from the fitted curve serves as an indicator of the critical turning point in the stabilized temperature, and the stress level associated with the minimum curvature is assumed to be the endurance limit. A detailed description of the M2 can be found in Ref [33] However, this method is not based on the same assumptions of the TCM and the OCM, regarding the use of a linear functions.

The variability in fatigue test results can often lead to significant uncertainties in data analysis. To overcome this challenge, mathematical models are developed to represent the fatigue behavior of the material, which are often characterized by several parameters. The maximum likelihood method (MLM) is a statistical technique commonly used to estimate these parameters based on experimental data. However, such estimates are subjected to uncertainty due to the variability in the measured data and model adequacy. Probabilistic models are developed to account for the uncertainty and provide a more comprehensive information related to model estimates. Monte Carlo Method (MCM) is used to generate probabilistic descriptions of the outcomes, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the variability and uncertainty in the test results. Here are some papers [5], [34], [35] that used MLM for fitting fatigue models and utilized uncertainty for estimating outcome of probabilistic models.

In this work, a statistical procedure based on the MLM is presented to estimate the model parameters and divide the dataset, stabilized temperature and maximum applied loading stress, into two subsets, leading to a unique estimation of the endurance limit. Moreover, a procedure is presented to determine the uncertainty of the estimation of the endurance limit using the MCM. The estimator of the endurance limit resulting from the proposed procedure is compared with the endurance limit estimated using the conventional and manual graphic method.

MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD METHOD

Lambert introduced the likelihood concept in 1760, and Fisher developed it in the previous century. The Maximum Likelihood Method is used to estimate the parameters of a model inferring experimental data. The likelihood function ($L(\theta)$) is a function of the model parameters, $\theta = \{\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n\}$, and it is proportional to the probability of the observed data:

$$L(\theta) \propto P(\text{Data}; \theta) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where P denotes the probability density function and Data are the experimental observations. The formal notation is

$$L(\theta; \text{Data}) = L(\theta; x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = L(\theta, x_1) \cdot L(\theta, x_2) \cdot \dots \cdot L(\theta, x_n) = \prod L(\theta, x_i) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are experimental data. The Log-likelihood function is often used instead of the likelihood function for computational reasons:

$$\text{Log}(\prod L(\theta; x_i)) = \sum \text{Log}(L(\theta, x_i)) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The model parameters are estimated by maximization of likelihood functions. In particular, the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) is the set of model parameters that maximizes the probability of the observed data. For a linear regression problem, the MLM leads to a least squares estimation if the error terms are assumed to be normally distributed with uniform variance. The equation proposed in the TCM is used here to formulate the following model:

$$\Delta T_{stab} = \max(m_1 \sigma_{max} + b_1 + \varepsilon_1(0, \sigma_1), m_2 \sigma_{max} + b_2 + \varepsilon_2(0, \sigma_2)) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where the model includes six parameters, m_1 is first slope; m_2 is second slope; (b_1) is intercept of the first line with the vertical axis; b_2 is intercept of the second line with the vertical axis; σ_1 is standard deviation of the first line; σ_2 is standard deviation of the second line; two random errors (ε), which are normally distributed with zero mean and variance equal to σ_1^2 or σ_2^2 depending on the line.

Fig. 2 Schematic of the model and parameters

The error is calculated as

$$\varepsilon = \Delta T_{stab} - \max(m_1 \sigma_{max} + b_1, m_2 \sigma_{max} + b_2) \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The maximization of the Likelihood is solved as a constrained minimization problem of negative logarithmic likelihood. In particular, the following constraints are formulated for the model parameters to optimize computational performance:.

$$\min_{\theta} \{-\text{Log}[L(\theta)]\} \quad \text{Subjected to} \quad \begin{cases} m_1 > 0 \\ m_1 < m_2 \leq m_{ff} \\ \sigma_1 > 0 \\ \sigma_2 > 0 \\ b_1 > b_2 \\ b_1 < \max(\Delta T_{stab}) \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where, m_{ff} , is a maximum slope between each pair of data. The constraints are justified by the following observations:

- Because of model assumptions and physical reasons, the stabilized temperature increases by increasing the applied stress amplitude, therefore m_1 and m_2 are positive. and, more specifically the second slope (m_2) is larger than the first slope (m_1).
- The second slope is bounded by m_{ff} , unless the data are perfectly aligned.
- The standard deviations must be positive by definition.
- Since $m_1 < m_2$, and the two lines cross each other for positive $\Delta T_{stab} > 0$ and $\sigma_{max} > 0$, the intercept of the first line b_1 is larger than the intercept of the second line b_2 . This is applicable for $R < 1$. For $R > 1$, i.e. compressive-compressive loading leading to a negative value of σ_{max} , $b_2 > b_1$, shall be selected as a constraint.
- The intercept of the first line cannot be larger than the max value of ΔT_{stab} , unless the data show a decreasing trend. For $R > 1$, $b_2 > \max(\Delta T_{stab})$, shall be selected as a constraint.

In order to determine the MLE, the minimization process is repeated 1000 times using a different starting point randomly selected between the constraints. The observed Fisher information matrix is determined from the second partial derivatives of the log likelihood function with respect to the model parameters at the MLE. The Hessian matrix is used to approximate the local behavior of the log-likelihood function near the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE). This information is used to estimate the uncertainty and the correlation underlying the model parameters. More information can be found in [36].

After solving the minimization problem, the set of model parameters that yields the smallest value for the negative logarithmic likelihood is selected as the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE). Upon selecting the smallest value for the negative logarithmic likelihood, the corresponding MLE, Hessian matrix, and likelihood value are saved. From the Hessian matrix calculated at $\hat{\theta}_{MLE}$, the covariance matrix of the model parameters is obtained, which are assumed to be distributed according to a multivariate normal distribution. The MCM is used to estimate the uncertainty underlying the estimation of the endurance limit, considering the input distribution of the parameters and the model of Equation 4. To obtain the probability distribution of the mean of the endurance limit, the MCM involves repeating simulations multiple times, allowing for the estimation of the statistical moments, such as the mean, standard deviation, and the probability density function, of the target quantity.

As a discussed before, in this model endurance limit is estimated as the abscissa of the point of intersection of the two lines:

$$\sigma_{max,0,TCM,ML} = \frac{b_2 - b_1 + \varepsilon(0, \sigma_2) - \varepsilon(0, \sigma_1)}{m_1 - m_2} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where $\sigma_{max,0,TCM,ML}$ represents the endurance limit estimated by the TCM, using the proposed ML framework.

The steps involved to estimate the aleatory uncertainty underlying the estimation of endurance limit are calculated by the following procedure:

- 1- Model parameters, $\hat{\theta}_{MLE} = \{b_1, m_1, \sigma_1, b_2, m_2, \sigma_2\}$, are obtained
- 2- two errors in model parameters are sampled by the following:
 - 2-1- a random numbers P_i , between 0 and 1 is generated
 - 2-2- then a standard normal deviate is calculated for both P_1 and P_2 , $s_i = \Phi^{-1}(P_i)$, where Φ^{-1} is the inverse of the Cdf of the standard normal distribution.
 - for fully correlated errors, σ_1 and σ_2 are multiplied by the same value of the inverse normal distribution

$$\sigma_{max,0,TCM,ML} = \frac{b_2 - b_1 + s \sigma_2 - s \sigma_1}{m_1 - m_2} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

- while for fully uncorrelated errors, σ_1 and σ_2 are multiplied by different values of the inverse normal distribution.

$$\sigma_{max,0,TCM,ML} = \frac{b_2 - b_1 + s_2 \sigma_2 - s_1 \sigma_1}{m_1 - m_2} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

3- intersection of two lines by considering errors and their distribution is calculated according to Equation 7

Steps 2 to 3 are repeated 100,000 times in a Monte Carlo simulation framework. As a result of this procedure, the distribution of the mean endurance limit is determined.

To account for the uncertainty of the model parameters in the estimation of the endurance limit, it is necessary to consider epistemic uncertainty. This involves the use of the multivariate normal distribution of parameters, $MVN(\hat{\theta}_{MLE}, COV_{\theta_{MLE}})$, where $COV_{\theta_{MLE}}$ is the covariance matrix obtained from the Fisher information Matrix [36], which approximates the local behavior of the log-likelihood function near the MLE. The steps 1-3 are repeated each time with a different parameter θ_{MLE} which is randomly drawn from the aforementioned distribution, thus providing a nested sampling scheme of epistemic and aleatory uncertainty, like in [35]. It should be mentioned that when the sampled θ_{MLE} contains parameters outside the boundaries of the domain as defined in Equation 6 this is disregarded.

ESTIMATION OF THE ENDURANCE LIMIT USING THE ML-BASED

In the following section, the statistical analysis is applied to the datasets obtained from the [37] in order to evaluate the methodology. The aim of this investigation is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the underlying procedures involved in the analysis of the dataset, thereby contributing to the advancement of the field. Therefore, the proposed framework based on the MLM is applied to estimate the model parameters.

a) b) Fig. 3 Comparing the empirical cumulative distribution function of endurance limit with a) aleatory and b) epistemic uncertainty for fully correlated and fully uncorrelated.

Fig. 3 depicts a comparison between fully correlated and fully uncorrelated instances of aleatory and epistemic uncertainty. The figure clearly demonstrates that the range of fully uncorrelated is wider compared to that of fully correlated uncertainty because correlation constrains the range of possible outcomes, narrowing the distribution, whereas uncorrelated variables can exhibit greater variation independently, leading to a wider distribution. The same holds for epistemic and aleatory uncertainty.

Table 1 Endurance limit obtained by conventional methods, TCM, Method 2 (M2) [33], and proposed framework based on TCM and MLM); NO. indicate the reference

NO.	Material	Unit	Method	$\sigma_{max,0}$	$\sigma_{max,0,TCM}$	$\sigma_{max,0,M2}$	$\sigma_{max,0,TCM,ML}$
[37]	CFRP	UTS %	S-N	60–65	64	58.21	64.21
[32]	stainless steel	MPa	TCM	-	357.48	336.45	357.91
[38]	CFRP (0°)	UTS %	TCM	-	73.8	69.25	74.48
[38]	CFRP ([0-90]°)	UTS %	TCM	-	53.8	48.57	56.76

[38]	CFRP ($\pm 45^\circ$)	UTS %	TCM	-	62.1	48.64	62.12
[39]	Crankshafts (5 kN rolling force)	N.m	Staircase	447.9	469	-	395.46
[39]	Crankshafts (10kN rolling force)	N.m	Staircase	571.0	585	574.75	574.68
[39]	Crankshafts (20 kN rolling force)	N.m	Staircase	684.4	663	591.90	699.69
[29]	CF/flax/epoxy	UTS %	S-N	50–55	51.25	-	51.28
[40]	AZ31B Mg alloy joint (as-welded)	MPa	S-N	59	63.7	54.83	63.41
[40]	AZ31B Mg alloy joint (ground flush)	MPa	S-N	59.9	65.6	61.27	74.44
[41]	martensitic stainless steels (ASTM A 182 F6NM)	MPa	Staircase	169.3	138.9	126.71	146.11
[42]	CFRP ($\pm 45^\circ$)	UTS %	S-N	65.6	63.7	52.26	67.2
[43]	GFRP 10J	MPa	TCM	-	64.17	67.81	57.58
[43]	GFRP 20J	MPa	TCM	-	60.97	66.03	60.79
[43]	GFRP 30J	MPa	TCM	-	59.88	50.00	56.89
[43]	GFRP 40J	MPa	TCM	-	52.67	54.45	55.01
[43]	CFRP 10J	MPa	TCM	-	144.12	133.53	127.26
[43]	CFRP 20J	MPa	TCM	-	117.05	115.47	111.33
[43]	CFRP 30J	MPa	TCM	-	114.10	-	126.21
[43]	CFRP 40J	MPa	TCM	-	101.09	-	110.95

A summary of the results including the endurance limit obtained using conventional method, TCM, M2, and MLE, is presented in Table 1. In Figure 4, the endurance limit derived using the staircase for the datasets in Table 1, is compared to the endurance limit derived by TCM, M2 as well as the estimator obtained by employing the proposed statistical model based on the MLM presented in this study. The relative error is defined as $(\sigma_0 - \hat{\sigma}_0)/\sigma_0$, where $\hat{\sigma}_0$ is either endurance limit, obtained by TCM, M2, and proposed framework based on TCM and MLM, depending on the method employed. It should be noted that both the TCM and the TCM,ML result in less bias as compared to M2 method. In terms of scatter, TCM,ML provides minimum scatter as compared to the other two methods. Therefore, the statistical model presented in this study is an effective alternative to the manual graphic method (user-dependency) as well as M2 to determine endurance limits applying on the thermography method. It may provide greater accuracy and efficiency in the analysis and works for all kinds of data sets.

Fig. 4 Comparison of endurance limits obtained from staircase method and TCM, M2, and TCM,ML methods

CONCLUSION

The present study introduces a statistical procedure based on the maximum likelihood method to analyze thermographic data, based on the two curve method. The proposed procedure, allows partitioning the dataset into two subsets avoiding user-dependency of the results. Therefore, the proposed approach leads to a unique estimation, and holds potential for enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the endurance limit. Furthermore, a procedure is presented for determining the uncertainty associated with the estimation of the endurance limit using the Monte Carlo method. The statistical analysis has been applied to the thermographic data obtained from previous studies in order to provide

a clear illustration of the procedure. Comparison is made with other two methods previously proposed in the literature revealing that the proposed framework shows less bias and reduces uncertainty. The results demonstrate that the statistical model proposed in this study can be successfully applied to all data. These findings highlight the potential of the proposed methodology as a valuable tool for estimating endurance limits in materials and enhancing the reliability and durability of various mechanical structures and potentially reducing testing efforts.

CITATIONS

- [1] D. S. Ivanov and S. v Lomov, "Modelling the structure and behaviour of 2D and 3D woven composites used in aerospace applications," in *Polymer composites in the aerospace industry*, Elsevier, 2015, pp. 21–52.
- [2] R. Figueiro, *Fibrous and composite materials for civil engineering applications*. Elsevier, 2011.
- [3] N. Tucker and K. Lindsey, *An introduction to automotive composites*. iSmithers Rapra Publishing, 2002.
- [4] F. G. Pascual and W. Q. Meeker, "Estimating fatigue curves with the random fatigue-limit model," *Technometrics*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 277–289, 1999.
- [5] D. Leonetti, J. Maljaars, and H. H. B. Snijder, "Fitting fatigue test data with a novel SN curve using frequentist and Bayesian inference," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 105, pp. 128–143, 2017.
- [6] Y. Qin, H. den Besten, S. Palkar, and M. L. Kaminski, "Mid-and high-cycle fatigue of welded joints in steel marine structures: effective notch stress and total stress concept evaluations," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 142, p. 105822, 2021.
- [7] O. I. de Normalización, *ISO 12107: Metallic Materials-Fatigue Testing-Statistical Planning and Analysis of Data*. ISO, 2003.
- [8] Y. Feng, C. Gao, Y. He, T. An, C. Fan, and H. Zhang, "Investigation on tension-tension fatigue performances and reliability fatigue life of T700/MTM46 composite laminates," *Compos Struct*, vol. 136, pp. 64–74, 2016.
- [9] E. Bayraktar, S. Antolonovich, and C. Bathias, "Multiscale study of fatigue behaviour of composite materials by χ -rays computed tomography," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 28, no. 10, pp. 1322–1333, 2006.
- [10] H. Zhang *et al.*, "Three-dimensional characterization of fatigue crack propagation behavior in an aluminum alloy using high resolution X-ray microtomography," in *Materials Science Forum*, Trans Tech Publ, 2010, pp. 378–383.
- [11] A. C. Batista, J. P. Nobre, D. F. C. Peixoto, L. A. A. Ferreira, P. M. S. T. de Castro, and L. Coelho, "X-ray diffraction residual stress measurements for assessment of rolling contact fatigue behaviour of railway steels," in *Advanced Materials Research*, Trans Tech Publ, 2014, pp. 782–787.
- [12] S. Y. Zamrik and R. N. Pangborn, "Fatigue damage assessment using X-ray diffraction and life prediction methodology," *Nuclear engineering and design*, vol. 116, no. 3, pp. 407–413, 1989.
- [13] S. Masmoudi, A. el Mahi, and S. Turki, "Fatigue behaviour and structural health monitoring by acoustic emission of E-glass/epoxy laminates with piezoelectric implant," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 108, pp. 50–58, 2016.
- [14] M. Burchak, I. R. Farrow, I. P. Bond, C. W. Rowland, and F. Menan, "Acoustic emission energy as a fatigue damage parameter for CFRP composites," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 457–470, 2007.
- [15] J. Kumar, S. Ahmad, C. K. Mukhopadhyay, T. Jayakumar, and V. Kumar, "Acoustic emission studies for characterization of fatigue crack growth behavior in HSLA steel," *Nondestructive Testing and Evaluation*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 77–96, 2016.
- [16] M. Mohammad, S. Abdullah, N. Jamaluddin, and O. Innayatullah, "Acoustic emission evaluation of fatigue life prediction for a carbon steel specimen using a statistical-based approach," *Materials Testing*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 487–495, 2013.

- [17] R. P. M. Janssen, L. E. Govaert, and H. E. H. Meijer, "An analytical method to predict fatigue life of thermoplastics in uniaxial loading: sensitivity to wave type, frequency, and stress amplitude," *Macromolecules*, vol. 41, no. 7, pp. 2531–2540, 2008.
- [18] N. v Akshantala and R. Talreja, "A micromechanics based model for predicting fatigue life of composite laminates," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 285, no. 1–2, pp. 303–313, 2000.
- [19] J. S. Park, S. J. Kim, K. H. Kim, S. H. Park, and C. S. Lee, "A microstructural model for predicting high cycle fatigue life of steels," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 27, no. 9, pp. 1115–1123, 2005.
- [20] K. Bao, Q. F. Wang, S. L. Liu, and Z. L. Wei, "Study on local strain field intensity approach for prediction fatigue life of crankshaft based on mechanical mechanics," in *Advanced Materials Research*, Trans Tech Publ, 2013, pp. 251–255.
- [21] L. Wang, B. Wang, S. Wei, Y. Hong, and C. Zheng, "Prediction of long-term fatigue life of CFRP composite hydrogen storage vessel based on micromechanics of failure," *Compos B Eng*, vol. 97, pp. 274–281, 2016.
- [22] A. Preumont and V. Piefort, "Predicting random high-cycle fatigue life with finite elements," 1994.
- [23] H. Dong, Z. Li, J. Wang, and B. L. Karihaloo, "A new fatigue failure theory for multidirectional fiber-reinforced composite laminates with arbitrary stacking sequence," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 87, pp. 294–300, 2016.
- [24] W. Lian and W. Yao, "Fatigue life prediction of composite laminates by FEA simulation method," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 123–133, 2010.
- [25] A. Geraci, G. La Rosa, and A. Risitano, "On the new methodology for the determination of the fatigue limit of materials using thermal infrared techniques," in *Risk minimization by experimental mechanics*, 1992.
- [26] M. P. Luong, "Infrared thermography of fatigue in metals," in *Thermosense XIV: An Intl Conf on Thermal Sensing and Imaging Diagnostic Applications*, SPIE, 1992, pp. 222–233.
- [27] C. Colombo *et al.*, "Efficient experimental methods for rapid fatigue life estimation of additive manufactured elements," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 167, p. 107345, 2023.
- [28] E. Z. Kordatos, K. G. Dassios, D. G. Aggelis, and T. E. Matikas, "Rapid evaluation of the fatigue limit in composites using infrared lock-in thermography and acoustic emission," *Mech Res Commun*, vol. 54, pp. 14–20, 2013.
- [29] Z. S. Bagheri, I. El Sawi, H. Bougherara, and R. Zdero, "Biomechanical fatigue analysis of an advanced new carbon fiber/flax/epoxy plate for bone fracture repair using conventional fatigue tests and thermography," *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater*, vol. 35, pp. 27–38, 2014.
- [30] S. Guo *et al.*, "Thermographic analysis of the fatigue heating process for AZ31B magnesium alloy," *Materials & Design (1980-2015)*, vol. 65, pp. 1172–1180, 2015.
- [31] Q. Guo, X. Guo, J. Fan, R. Syed, and C. Wu, "An energy method for rapid evaluation of high-cycle fatigue parameters based on intrinsic dissipation," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 80, pp. 136–144, 2015.
- [32] Q. Guo and X. Guo, "Research on high-cycle fatigue behavior of FV520B stainless steel based on intrinsic dissipation," *Mater Des*, vol. 90, pp. 248–255, 2016.
- [33] J. Huang, M.-L. Pastor, C. Garnier, and X. Gong, "Rapid evaluation of fatigue limit on thermographic data analysis," *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 104, pp. 293–301, 2017.
- [34] D. Leonetti, J. Maljaars, and H. H. B. Snijder, "Fracture mechanics based fatigue life prediction for a weld toe crack under constant and variable amplitude random block loading—Modeling and uncertainty estimation," *Eng Fract Mech*, vol. 242, p. 107487, 2021.

- [35] D. Leonetti, J. Maljaars, and H. H. Snijder, “Probabilistic fatigue resistance model for steel welded details under variable amplitude loading–Inference and uncertainty estimation,” *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 135, p. 105515, 2020.
- [36] Y. Pawitan, *In all likelihood: statistical modelling and inference using likelihood*. Oxford University Press, 2001.
- [37] J. Montesano, Z. Fawaz, and H. Bougherara, “Use of infrared thermography to investigate the fatigue behavior of a carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite,” *Compos Struct*, vol. 97, pp. 76–83, 2013.
- [38] J. Huang, C. Li, and W. Liu, “Investigation of internal friction and fracture fatigue entropy of CFRP laminates with various stacking sequences subjected to fatigue loading,” *Thin-Walled Structures*, vol. 155, p. 106978, 2020.
- [39] J. J. R. Faria *et al.*, “Determination of the fatigue behavior of mechanical components through infrared thermography,” *Eng Fail Anal*, vol. 134, p. 106018, 2022.
- [40] H. X. Zhang, G. H. Wu, Z. F. Yan, S. F. Guo, P. D. Chen, and W. X. Wang, “An experimental analysis of fatigue behavior of AZ31B magnesium alloy welded joint based on infrared thermography,” *Mater Des*, vol. 55, pp. 785–791, 2014.
- [41] R. De Finis, D. Palumbo, F. Ancona, and U. Galietti, “Fatigue limit evaluation of various martensitic stainless steels with new robust thermographic data analysis,” *Int J Fatigue*, vol. 74, pp. 88–96, 2015.
- [42] J. Huang, C. Garnier, M.-L. Pastor, and X. Gong, “Investigation of self-heating and life prediction in CFRP laminates under cyclic shear loading condition based on the infrared thermographic data,” *Eng Fract Mech*, vol. 229, p. 106971, 2020.
- [43] A. Katunin, I. Pivdiablyk, L. Gornet, and P. Rozycki, “A hybrid method for determination of fatigue limit and non-destructive evaluation of composite structures after low-velocity impact loading,” *Compos B Eng*, vol. 238, p. 109898, 2022.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work was supported by Interreg North-West Europe (NWE993).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.